

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1925	A. Kimball Romney	1947	1956	1995		American social sciences professor and one of the founders of cognitive anthropology	
1925	Zigmas Zinkevičius	1948	1955	2018		Lithuanian linguist-historian (history of languages, onomastics and other areas)	1925-2018
1925	Kathleen Gough	1948	1950	1990	w	British anthropologist and feminist	1925-1990
1925	Ida Rodríguez Prampolini	1948	1948	1987	w	Mexican academic, art historian and cultural preservationist, who was heavily involved in the creation of organizations and institutions to preserve the artistic traditions of Mexico	1925-2017
1925	Johannes Erben	1949	1949	1990		German Germanist and linguist	
1925	Karel Werner	1950		1990		Czech indologist, orientalist, religious studies scholar, and philosopher of religion	1925-2019
1925	Rolf Rendtorff	1950	1950	1990		German Professor of Old Testament	1925-2014
1925	Henry Kučera	1951	1952	1990		Czech-American linguist (computational linguistics)	1925-2010
1925	Moshe Goshen-Gottstein	1951	1951	1991		German-Israeli professor of Semitic linguistics and biblical philology	1925-1991
1925	G. William Skinner	1951	1954	2005		American anthropologist and scholar of China	1925-2008
1925	Dušan Zbavitel	1951	1954	1985		Czech Indologist	1925-2012
1925	Ivan Morris	1951	1951	1976		British author and teacher in the field of Japanese Studies	1925-1976
1925	Max Imdahl	1951	1951	1988		German art historian specialized in art historical methodology and the interpretation of modern art after World War II	1925-1988
1925	Luís Lindley Cintra	1951	1951	1991		Portuguese prominent figure in Portuguese philology and linguistics	1925-1991
1925	Bruce Haywood	1951	1956	1994		British-American professor of German language and literature	1925-2020
1925	MAK Halliday	1952	1955	1987		British English-Australian linguist (internationally influential systemic functional linguistics model of language)	1925-2018
1925	Roger Brown	1952	1952	1995		American social psychologist (children)	1925-1997
1925	Amir-Hossein Aryanpour	1952	1952	1976		Iranian lexicographer, writer, translator, philosopher, sociologist, and literary figure	1925-2001

1925 Siegbert Salomon Praver	1952	1953	1992	German the Taylor Professor of the German Language and Literature	1925-2012
1925 Albrecht Schöne	1952	1952	1990	German professor of German philology	1925-1978
1925 Rosemary Woolf	1953 No		1978 w	British scholar of medieval literature	
1925 Jackson Bailey	1953	1959	1994	American academic, noted expert in Japanese history, culture, and Japanese-American relations	1925-1996
1925 Giovanni Battista Bronzini	1953		2002	Italian anthropologist and historian of Italian folk traditions	1925-2002
1925 Lloyd Fallers	1953	1953	1974	American the A. A. Michelson Distinguished Service Professor in the departments of anthropology and sociology	1925-1974
1925 Francis Clark Howell	1953	1953	1991	American anthropologist	1925-2007
1925 Manfred Fuhrmann	1953	1953	1990	German professor for classical Latin philology and one of the most eminent German philologists	1925-2005
1925 Kenneth Roy Norman	1954 No		1992	British philologist	1925-2002
1925 Henrik Birnbaum	1954	1954	2002	American linguist, Slavist and historian	
1925 Thomas J. King Jr.	1954	1963	1992	American educator, and an early user of word processing and sequence analysis to compare available early versions of William Shakespeare's plays for identification of variant texts and their analysis	
1925 Daniel P. Biebuyck	1954	1954	1989	Belgian authority on central African art with contributions to contextual African art studies, oral literature, and the sociopolitical structure of numerous groups in DRC	1925-1994
1925 Yolanda Murphy	1954		2004 w	American cultural anthropologist who is the co-author of classic anthropology text Women of the Forest with her husband, Robert F. Murphy	1925-2019
1925 Yuri Bregel	1955	1961	1997	Russian one of the world's leading historians of Islamic Central Asia	1925-2016
1925 Otto Friedrich August Meinardus	1955	1955	2005	German Coptologist and pastor	1925-2005
1925 Ingrid Brainard	1956	1956	2000 w	German musicologist, dance historian, performer, and teacher of historical dance	1925-2000
1925 Peter Ladefoged	1957	1959	1991	British linguist and phonetician	1925-2006
1925 Ernest Gellner	1957	1961	1993	British-Czech philosopher and social anthropologist	1925-1995

1925 M. Margaret Clark	1957	1957	1991 w	American medical anthropologist who is credited with founding the sub-discipline of medical anthropology	1925-2003
1925 Anthony Leeds	1957	1957	1989	American anthropologist best known for his work in the favelas of Rio de Janeiro and on urban-rural relations in Brazil	1925-1989
1925 Božidar Finka	1959	1960	1991	Croatian linguist and lexicographer	1925-1999
1925 Henry F. Dobyns	1960	1960	1989	American anthropologist, author and researcher specializing in the ethnohistory and demography of native peoples in the American hemisphere	1925-2009
1925 Victor Hanzeli	1961	1969	1991	Hungarian linguist and professor of Romance Languages and Literature	1925-1991
1925 Moni Nag	1961	1961	1998	Indian anthropologist (politics of sexuality), pioneer of demographic anthropology	1925-2015
1925 Conrad Brann	1961		2000	German-British linguist	1925-2014
1925 Robin Nisbet	1961		1992	British classicist and academic, specialising in Latin literature	1925-2013
1925 Stjepan Babić	1962	1962	1991	Croatian linguist	
1925 Eldred D. Jones	1962	1962	2006	Sierra Leonean academic and literary critic.	
1925 J. Marvin Brown	1962	1962	1995	American linguist (evolution of Thai and related languages)	1925-2002
1925 Sarah Israelit Groll	1963	1963	1994 w	Israeli Egyptologist and linguist	1925-2007
1925 Claude Meillassoux	1964	1964	1998	French neo-Marxist economic anthropologist and Africanist	1925-2005
1925 Ray Matheny	1968	1968	2016	American emeritus professor of anthropology at Brigham Young University (BYU)	
1925 Маргарита Кожина	1968		1993	Russian linguist	1925-2012
1925 Lydia T. Black	1971	1973	1998 w	Ukrainian-American anthropologist	
1925 Astri Riddervold	1975 No		1997 w	Norwegian anthropologist, leader in Norwegian food traditions and food culture	
1925 Otto von Sadvoszky	1976	1976	1994	Hungarian-American anthropologist	
1926 Robert McCormick Adams Jr.	1941	1957	1994	American anthropologist and Secretary of the Smithsonian Institution (1984–94)	1926-2018

1926 Harold C. Conklin	1948	1955	1996	American anthropologist who conducted extensive ethnoecological and linguistic field research in Southeast Asia (particularly the Philippines) and was a pioneer of ethnoscience, documenting indigenous ways of understanding and knowing the world	1926-2016
1926 Petr Sgall	1949	1949	1992	Czech linguist	1926-2019
1926 Elfriede Moser-Rath	1949	1949	1993 w	Austrian ethnologist (folk tales), and early modern literature	1926-1993
1926 Uriel Weinreich	1949	1951	1967	Polish-American linguist (Yiddish studies, sociolinguistics, and dialectology)	1926-1967
1926 Helmut Rix	1950	1950	1993	German linguist (Indo-European and Etruscan languages)	1926-2004
1926 Joshua Fishman	1950	1953	1992	American linguist (sociology of language, language planning, bilingual education, and language and ethnicity.)	1926-2015
1926 Wolfgang Iser	1950	1950	1991	German literature scholar	1926-2007
1926 Ludo Rocher	1950	1950	2002	Belgian-American eminent Sanskrit scholar, and the W. Norman Brown Professor Emeritus of South Asia Studies	1926-2016
1926 Elfriede Knauer	1951	1951	1986 w	German Classicist and Ancient historian specialising in Greek vase painting, the survival of classical themes in Renaissance art, the history of cartography, classical influences on Central and East Asian art, and the Silk Road	1926-2010
1926 Antonín Bartoněk	1952	1952	1990	Czech classical philologist and a specialist in Mycenaean studies	1926-2016
1926 Karl Kroeber	1952	1956	2008	American literary scholar, known for his writing on the English Romantics and American Indian literature	1926-2009
1926 Karl Beckson	1952	1959	2004	American educator, scholar, and author of numerous articles and sixteen books on British literature, culture	1926-2008
1926 Chie Nakane	1952	1952	1987 w	Japanese anthropologist and Professor Emerita of Social Anthropology	
1926 Malkhaz Abdushelishvili	1952	1952	1998	Georgian scientist, one of the founders of the Georgian scientific school of Anthropology, Academician of the Georgian Academy of Sciences (GAS)	1926-1998

1926	William T. Sanders	1952	1957	1994	American anthropologist who specialized in the archaeology of Mesoameric	1926-2008
1926	Georg Nicolaus Knauer	1952	1952	1988	German-American classical philologist	1926-2018
1926	William C. Sturtevant	1953	1955	1996	American anthropologist and ethnologist, linguist	1926-2007
1926	Jane Carter Goodale	1953	1959	1995 w	American anthropologist, author, photographer, and professor who worked to bring attention to the roles of women in Oceania and Australia through her extensive research in the field of ethnography	1926-2008
1926	Georg Luck	1953	1953	1990	Swiss classicist known for his studies of magical beliefs and practices in the Classical world	1926-2013
1926	Beda Allemann	1953	1953	1991	Swiss Literary scholar and university lecturer	1926-1991
1926	Klaus Koch	1953	1953	2005	German Old Testament scholar	1926-2019
1926	Muḥsin Maḥdī	1954	1954	1996	Iraqi-American islamologist and arabist	1926-2007
1926	Margarita Rudenko	1954	1954	1976	Russian philologist, Orientalist, Kurdologist (specialist for Kurdish language, culture and history), literature researcher and ethnographer	1926-1976
1926	Robbins Burling	1955	1958	1995	American professor of anthropology and sociolinguistics	
1926	Knut Kleve	1955	1955	1996	Norwegian classical philologist	1926-2017
1926	Maurice Pope	1955		1988	South African-British linguist, specialist in Classical studies and antiquity, one of leading researchers of the Cretan script Linear A	1926-2019
1926	Carl Hovde	1955	1955	1995	American educator and former dean of Columbia College	1926-2009
1926	V. H. Viglielmo	1955	1955	2002	American prominent scholar and translator of Japanese literature and works of Japanese philosophy	1926-2016
1926	Vytautas Mažiulis	1956	1956	1996	Lithuanian Balticist (Old Prussian language and Indo-European languages)	1926-2009
1926	Robert A. Bryan	1956	1956	1991	American former university professor, administrator and university president	1926-2017
1926	William E. Skillend	1956	1956	1989	British academic specializing in the Korean language, and the first professor of Korean at SOAS	1926-2010
1926	Richard Frank Salisbury	1956	1957	1989	Canadian anthropologist, specializing in the field of Economic anthropology and anthropology of development	1926-1989

1926 Miguel León-Portilla	1956	1956	1995	Mexican anthropologist and historian, authorities on Aztec culture and literature in the pre-Columbian and colonial eras among Mexican academia	1926-2019
1926 H. Clyde Wilson Jr.	1956	1961	1997	American professor of anthropology	1926-2010
1926 Neculai Alexandru Ursu	1957	1967	2016	Romanian linguist, philologist, and literary historian	1926-2016
1926 Jože Toporišič	1957	1963	1990	Slovenian linguist	1926-2014
1926 Wilfred G. Lambert	1957		1993	British historian and archaeologist, a specialist in Assyriology and Near Eastern Archaeology	1926-2011
1926 Mario Alinei	1958	1971	1996	Italian linguist, pioneer in the use of computers in linguistics	1926-2018
1926 Aleksandr Matveyev	1959		2010	Russian linguist (toponomics, onomastics, etymology)	1926-2010
1926 Derek Bickerton	1959	1976	1999	British English-American linguist and academic	1926-2018
1926 Harold A. Gould	1959	1959	1991	American anthropologist specializing in Indian society and civilization	
1926 George Avery	1959	1959	1994	American professor for German Studies	1926-2004
1926 Martin Hengel	1959	1959	1992	German historian of religion, focusing on the "Second Temple Period" or "Hellenistic Period" of early Judaism and Christianity	1926-2009
1926 Luise Anna Hercus	1960	1976	1990 w	Australian-German linguist	1926-2018
1926 Marian Robertson Wilson	1960	1960	1992 w	American cellist, linguist and teacher most notable role as music editor of the eight-volume Coptic Encyclopedia	1926-2013
1926 Miguel Civil	1960	1966	2001	American expert on Sumer and Ancient Mesopotamian studies at the University of Chicago Oriental Institute	1926-2019
1926 Margaret Langdon	1960	1966	1991 w	American linguist	1926-2005
1926 Russell Jones	1961	1961	1984	British Orientalist who has researched Malay and Indonesian languages and culture in the broad sense	1926-2019
1926 Sev'yan I. Vainshtein	1961	1961	1997	Russian ethnographer, archaeologist, historian and explorer of Siberian and Central Asian peoples	1926-2008
1926 Hans Ras	1962	1966	1992	Dutch emeritus professor of Javanese language and literature	1926-2003

1926	Dorothy E. Smith	1963	1963	2000 w	Canadian sociologist with research interests in a variety of disciplines, including women's studies, feminist theory, psychology, and educational studies, as well as in certain subfields of sociology, such as the sociology of knowledge, family studies, and methodology.	
1926	Harold Crane Fleming	1964	1964	2008	American anthropologist and historical linguist	1926-2015
1926	Farman Fatehpuri	1965	1965	1986	Indian-Pakistani eminent Urdu linguist, researcher, writer, critic and scholar of Pakistan	1926-2013
1926	Roy Rappaport	1966	1966	1996	American anthropologist known for his contributions to the anthropological study of ritual and to ecological anthropology	1926-1997
1926	Eleanor Zelliot	1969	1969	1997 w	American writer, professor of Carleton College and specialist on the history of India, Southeast Asia, Vietnam, women of Asia, Untouchables, and social movements	1926-2016
1926	Christian-Joseph Guyonvarc'h	1973		1988	French philologist	
1926	Anna Lou Dehavenon	1978	1978	2000 w	American urban anthropologist	
1927	Antonio Garzya	1949	1949	2007	Italian emeritus professor of Greek literature, classical scholar, philologist, and specialist in ancient Greek and Byzantine studies	1927-2012
1927	Samuel G. Armistead	1950	1955	2010	American ethnographer, linguist, folklorist, historian, literary critic and professor of Spanish	1927-2013
1927	Richard Pankhurst	1951	1956	2008	British academic, founding member of the Institute of Ethiopian Studies	1927-2017
1927	Kamil Zvelebil	1951	1952	1992	Czech scholar in Indian literature and linguistics, notably Tamil, Sanskrit, Dravidian linguistics and literature and philology	1927-2009
1927	Audrey Henshall	1951		1993 w	British English archaeologist known for her work on Scottish chambered cairns, prehistoric pottery and early textiles, including clothing found preserved in peat bogs	
1927	Herbert Pilch	1952	1957	1995	German linguist and celtologist	1927-2018
1927	Frederick William Ratcliffe	1952	1952	1994	British philologist and librarian	
1927	Paul Pimsleur	1952	1956	1976	American scholar in the field of applied linguistics	1927-1976

1927 Paul Friedrich	1952	1957	2005	American anthropologist, linguist, poet, and Professor of Social Thought	1927-2016
1927 Barbara Mertz	1952	1952	1978 w	American Egyptologist and novelist	1927-2013
1927 Erika Simon	1952	1952	1983 w	German scholar of classical archaeology	1927-2019
1927 Milan Moguš	1953	1962	1992	Croatian linguist	1927-2017
1927 Marvin Harris	1953	1953	2000	American anthropologist (Contributions to the development of cultural materialism)	1927-2001
1927 Arthur Terry	1953	No	1993	British philologist, critic and translator, expert in Catalan literature	1927-2004
1927 Helge Nordahl	1953	1953	1996	Norwegian philologist	1927-2018
1927 Jan W. Dietrichson	1953	1953	1997	Norwegian philologist	
1927 Susan M. Ervin-Tripp	1953	1955	1996 w	American linguist (psycholinguistic and sociolinguistic)	1927-2018
1927 Rudolf Krajčovič	1953	1953	1999	Slovak linguist and Slavist, the author of migration-integration theory about the origin of the Slovak	1927-2014
1927 Pavle Merkuš	1953	1960	1990	Slovenian-Italian composer, ethnomusicologist, Slovene specialist, and etymologist	1937-2014
1927 Dell Hymes	1954	1955	1998	American linguist, sociolinguist, anthropologist, and folklorist	1927-2009
1927 Endel Tulving	1954	1957	2006	Estonian-Canadian experimental psychologist and cognitive neuroscientist	
1927 Florence M. Voegelin	1954	1954	1987 w	American anthropologist and linguist	1927-1989
1927 Jacqueline Roumeguere-Eberhardt	1954	1954	2002 w	South African-French anthropologist	1927-2006
1927 Ivar Eskeland	1955	1955	1986	Norwegian philologist, publisher, translator, biographer, literary critic, newspaper editor, theatre worker, radio personality and organizational leader	1927-2005
1927 Robert J. Smith	1955	1955	1997	American the Goldwin Smith Professor of Anthropology	1927-2016
1927 Paul T. Baker	1955	1956	1987	American the Evan Pugh Professor Emeritus of Anthropology, one of the most influential biological anthropologists of his generation	1927-2007
1927 Lev Kleyn	1955	1976	1997	Russian archaeologist, anthropologist and philologist	1927-2019
1927 Ursula Cowgill	1956	1956	2003 w	American biologist and anthropologist	1927-2015
1927 Edwin Ardener	1956		1987	British social anthropologist	1927-1987
1927 Camil Mureșanu	1957	1971	2015	Romanian historian, professor, author, and translator	1927-2015

1927 Patrick Hanan	1957	1961	1997	N New Zealand scholar of Chinese literature, the Victor S. Thomas Professor of Chinese Literature	1927-2014
1927 Wallace Chafe	1958	1958	1991	American linguist (semantics)	1927-2019
1927 Stefan Radt	1958	1958	1987	Dutch historian, author and academic specializing in ancient Greek geography	1927-2017
1927 G. Ainsworth Harrison	1958	1958	1994	British English biological anthropologist	1927-2017
1927 James Morris Blaut	1958	1958	1997	American professor of anthropology and geography	1927-2000
1927 Ninian Smart	1958		1989	British Scottish writer and university educator, pioneer in the field of secular religious studies	1927-2001
1927 Rodolphe Kasser	1959	1964	1998	Swiss philologist and archaeologist, Coptic scholar (The Gospel of Judas)	1927-2013
1927 Osamu Fujimura	1959	1962	2004	Japanese physicist, phonetician and linguist, one of the pioneers of speech science	1927-2017
1927 Stanley Wolpert	1959	1959	2002	American historian, Indologist, and author on the political and intellectual history of modern India and Pakistan	1927-2019
1927 W. F. H. Nicolaisen	1960		1992	German folklorist, linguist, medievalist, scholar of onomastics and literature, educator, and author with specialties in Scottish and American studies	1927-2016
1927 June Nash	1960	1960	1995 w	American social and feminist anthropologist and Distinguished Professor Emerita	1927-2019
1927 Robert L. Hall	1960	1960	1998	American anthropologist	1927-2012
1927 Arne Martin Klausen	1961	1968	1995	Norwegian social anthropologist.	1927-2018
1927 Sidney Moko Mead	1961	1968	1990	New Zealand anthropologist, historian, artist, teacher, writer and prominent Māori leader	
1927 Douglass Stott Parker, Sr.	1961		2007	American classicist, academic, and translator	1927-2011
1927 Madeleine Mathiot	1962	1965	1994 w	American Professor Emerita of Linguistics	
1927 Michael Day	1962	1962	1989	British anatomist and paleoanthropologist	1927-2018
1927 Lambros Comitas	1962	1962	2001	American the Gardner Cowles Professor of Anthropology and Education	1927-2020
1927 R. Tom Zuidema	1962	1962	1993	Dutch-American professor of Anthropology and Latin American and Caribbean Studies	1927-2016
1927 Kenneth Goodman	1963	1966	1998	American Professor Emeritus, Language Reading and Culture	1927-2020
1927 William Labov	1963	1964	2015	American linguist, founder of the discipline of variationist sociolinguistics	

1927 Gyula Király	1964	1969	1996	Hungarian literary historian	1927-2011
1927 Talat Tekin	1965	1965	1994	Turkish linguist, researcher and writer with important contributions to Turkish literature	1927-2015
1927 Elizabeth Warnock Fernea	1965	1965	1999 w	American influential writer and filmmaker who spent much of her life in the field producing numerous ethnographies and films that capture the struggles and turmoil of African and Middle Eastern cultures	1927-2008
1927 Pinkney L. Near	1965		1990	American curator of the Cincinnati Museum of Art and afterward curator of the Virginia Museum of Fine Arts	1927-1990
1927 Kjell Venås	1967	1967	1987	Norwegian philologist	1927-2018
1927 David M. Brugge	1967 No		1988	American cultural anthropologist, ethnohistorian, linguist, archaeologist (Navajo)	1927-2013
1927 Ignatius Mattingly	1968	1968	1996	American linguist and speech scientist	1927-2004
1928 Thomas Barth	1948	1959	1995	Norwegian social anthropologist and ethnographician	1928-2016
1928 Mazzino Montinari	1949	1949	1986	Italian scholar of Germanistics, marxist	1928-1986
1928 Diego Catalán	1949	1951	1998	Spanish Romanist, Hispanist and Medievalist	1928-2008
1928 William Bright	1950	1955	1988	American linguist who specialized in Native American and South Asian language	1928-2006
1928 David Glenn Hays	1951	1956	1980	American linguist, computer scientist and social scientist	1928-1995
1928 Noam Chomsky	1951	1955	2005	American linguist, philosopher	
1928 William J. Samarin	1951	1962	1991	American linguist and academic	1928-2020
1928 Manuel Reymundo	1952	1952	1993	Spanish lexicographer, linguist and philologist	
1928 Peter H. Feist	1952	1958	1993	German art historian	1928-2015
1928 Jean-Marie Zemb	1953	1955	1986	French linguist and Germanist	1928-2007
1928 John Wansbrough	1953		1992	American historian who taught at the University of London's School of Oriental and African Studies (SOAS)	1928-2002
1928 Tatsuo Nishida	1953	1962	1992	Japanese linguist (Tangut language)	1928-2012
1928 Helmut Gneuss	1953		1997	German scholar of Anglo-Saxon and Latin manuscripts and literature	
1928 David Francis Pocock	1953		1987	British anthropologist whose main field of study was the people and diaspora of the Indian state of Gujarat	1928-2007
1928 Joan Carter	1954	1971	1995 w	British-American Linguist (Bantu languages, Shona, Kongo and Tonga)	1928-2016

1928	William Kelly Simpson	1954	1954	2004	American professor of Egyptology, Archaeology, Ancient Egyptian literature, and Afro-Asiatic languages at Yale University	1928-2017
1928	Emmanuel Poulle	1954	1954	2005	French archivist and historian, specialist in the history of science and the medieval period	1928-2011
1928	John Blacking	1954	1965	1990	British ethnomusicologist and social anthropologist	1928-1990
1928	Nicholas Heer	1955	1955	1990	Former researcher of Near Eastern Languages and Civilization, Arabic language and literature, Islamic theology and philosophy	
1928	William Ayres Ward	1955	1958	1986	American Egyptologist	1928-1996
1928	John Emerton	1955		1995	British Anglican priest, theologian, and academic	1928-2015
1928	Alice Dewey	1955	1959	2005 w	American anthropologist who studied Javanese society	1928-2017
1928	Margret Schleidt	1955	1955	1990 w	German human ethologist	1928-2012
1928	Vera Mae Green	1955	1969	1982 w	American anthropologist, educator, and scholar, who made major contributions in the fields of Caribbean studies, interethnic studies, black family studies and the study of poverty and the poor	1928-1982
1928	Lorenz Dittmann	1955	1955	1996	German art historian	1928-2018
1928	Georgy Klimov	1955	1955	1997	Russian linguist and a leading specialist of the Caucasian languages	1928-1997
1928	Eileen Bowser	1956		1992 w	American film archivist and a leader of the international film archive movement	1928-2019
1928	Kurt Mueller-Vollmer	1956	1962	2016	American philosopher and professor of German Studies & Humanities	1928-2019
1928	William W. Hallo	1956	1956	2002	German-American professor of Assyriology and Babylonian Literature and curator of the Babylonian collection at Yale University	1928-2015
1928	Stephen Porter Dunn	1956	1959	1987	American anthropologist specializing in ethnic groups of the Soviet Union	1928-1999
1928	Emily Vermeule	1956	1956	1994 w	American classical scholar and archaeologist	1928-2001
1928	Herbert Morris	1956	1956	1993	American philosopher, literary critic and art historian	
1928	Kurt Treu	1956	1956	1989	Estonian-German classical philologist	1928-1991
1928	Peter Lienhardt	1957	1957	1993	British social anthropologist	1928-1986
1928	Frank B. Livingstone	1957	1957	1998	American Professor Emeritus of Anthropology	1928-2005

1928	Rolf Knierim	1957		1997	German-American theologian and biblical scholar who specialized in the research of the Old Testament	1928-2018
1928	Maria Ester Grebe Vicuna	1958	1980	2008 w	Chilean ethnomusicologist and anthropologist	1928-2012
1928	Park Honan	1959	1959	1993	American academic and author	1928-2014
1928	William P. Malm	1959	1959	2004	American musicologist known for his studies of Japanese traditional music	
1928	Andrew Walls	1959		1995	British historian of missions, best known for his pioneering studies of the history of the African church and a pioneer in the academic field of World Christianity	
1928	Norman Zide	1960	1960	1993	American Professor Emeritus of the Department of South Asian Languages & Civilization	
1928	Sture Allén	1960	1965	1993	Swedish professor of computational linguistics	
1928	George W. Stocking Jr.	1960	1960	2000	German-American scholar noted for his scholarship on the history of anthropology	1928-2013
1928	John Langston Gwaltney	1960	1967	1987	American Afro blind writer and anthropologist focused on African-American culture	1928-1998
1928	Luis Kemnitzer	1960	1960	1994	American anthropologist known for his social and political activism	1928-2006
1928	Oswald Werner	1961	1963	1998	Slovakian-American Professor of Anthropology and Linguistics	
1928	William M. Bass	1961	1961	1995	American forensic anthropologist, best known for his research on human osteology and human decomposition	
1928	Jeremy Boissevain	1962	1962	2002	Dutch anthropologist	1928-2015
1928	Kiyozō Kazama	1962	1978	1988	Japanese professor comparative linguistics	
1928	Julia Sutton	1962	1962	1997 w	American musicologist and historian of early dance and music	1928-2012
1928	Masao Miyoshi	1964	1964	2000	Japanese-American scholar of literature and culture and Hajime Mori Endowed Chair in Japanese Language and Literature	1928-2009
1928	Serge Lancel	1964		1997	French archaeologist, historian and philologist	1928-2005
1928	Nicola Tanda	1965	No	2016	Italian philologist and literary critic (expert of the literary theory of 19th-century Italian authors), editor	1928-2016
1928	Geert Hofstede	1966	1967	2017	Dutch social psychologist	
1928	Robert Jaulin	1967		1996	French ethnologist	1928-1996

1928	Günter Lüling	1970	1970	1991	German Protestant theologian, philological scholar (Dr. in Arabistics and Islamics) and pioneer in the study of early Islamic origins.	
1928	Alegría Bendayán de Bendelac	1970	1980	1992 w	Venezuelan philologist, professor, writer and Jewish poet	
1928	Anne de Coursey Clapp	1971	1975	1999 w	American scholar in art history , teacher, and writer (Chinese art history)	
1928	Pierre Sansot	1971		1998	French anthropologist and sociologist	
1928	Mayotte Bollack	1971		1988 w	French professor of philology	
1928	Harry Smith	1974		1988	British Egyptologist and academic, specialising in epigraphy and Egyptian archaeology	
1928	Eloina Miyares Bermudez	1975	No	2003 w	Cuban linguist and academician	
1929	Julia Elena Fortún	1946		1989 w	Bolivian historian, anthropologist, folklorist, and ethnomusicologist, pioneer in this last field in her country	1929-2016
1929	M. A. R. Barker	1951	1959	1992	American linguist and writer (Urdu language, Indian languages)	1929-2012
1929	Riekele Borger	1952	1952	1997	Dutch-German Assyriologist educated in the German tradition	1929-2010
1929	George Steiner	1952	1955	1994	American Franco-American literary critic, essayist, philosopher, novelist, and educator	1929-2020
1929	Leon Stover	1952	1963	1995	American anthropologist, a Sinologist, and a science fiction fan, who wrote both fiction and nonfiction	1929-2006
1929	Josette Rey-Debove	1953	1968	2005 w	French lexicographer and semiologist, the first female lexicographer in France (feminist in french)	1929-2005
1929	Geoffrey Hartman	1953	1953	2009	German-American literary theorist	1929-2016
1929	Dionýz Ďurišin	1954		1997	Slovak literary theorist and comparatist	1929-1997
1929	Péter Szondi	1954	1954	1971	Hungarian celebrated literary scholar and philologist	1929-1971
1929	Raymond Chevallier	1954		1997	French historian, archaeologist and Latinist	1929-2004
1929	Stanley Jeyaraja Tambiah	1954	1954	2005	Sri Lankan social anthropologist and Esther and Sidney Rabb Professor (Emeritus) of Anthropology at Harvard University	1929-2014
1929	Hellmut Flashar	1954	1954	1997	German classical philologist and translator	
1929	Vyacheslav Ivanov	1955	1955	2015	Russian philologist, semiotician and Indo-Europeanist	1929-2017
1929	John Andrew Frey	1955	1957	1997	American philologist	1929-1997

1929	Carl Croneberg	1955	No	1986	Swedish-American Deaf linguist known for his work on American Sign Language (ASL)	
1929	Karl Rudolf Walther Ludwig	1955	1955	1994	German Classic and neo-Latin philologist	
1929	Jean Mandler	1956	1956	2000	w	American Professor of Cognitive Science
1929	Sydney Lamb	1957	1958	1992		American linguist (stratificational grammar, Native American languages, historical linguistics, computational linguistics)
1929	Warren Cowgill	1957	1957	1985		American linguist (Indo-European linguistics) 1929-1985
1929	Magnus Ulleland	1957	1957	1996		Norwegian philologist, translator 1929-2016
1929	Winfried Bühler	1957	1957	1991		German classical philologist 1929-2010
1929	Rebecca Posner	1958	1958	1996	w	British philologist, linguist and academic (Romance languages) 1929-2018
1929	Franklin Southworth	1958	1958	1998		American linguist and Professor Emeritus of South Asian linguistics
1929	Anton Moeliono	1958	1981	1990		Indonesian linguist 1929-2011
1929	Brunilde Sismondo Ridgway	1958	1958	1994	w	Italian archaeologist and specialist in ancient Greek sculpture
1929	Karl Pestalozzi	1958	1958	1999		Swiss Literary scholar
1929	Aravind Joshi	1959	1960	2012		Indian-American computational linguist 1929-2017
1929	Emmon Bach	1959	1959	1992		American linguist 1929-2014
1929	Anna Czekanowska-Kuklińska	1959	1959	2004	w	Polish musicologist and ethnographer
1929	Fernando Silva Santisteban	1959	1959	2006		Peruvian historian, anthropologist and professor 1929-2006
1929	Michael D. Coe	1959	1959	1994		American archaeologist, anthropologist, epigrapher and author (pre-Columbian Mesoamerica, particularly the Maya, and was among the foremost Mayanists of the late 20th century) 1929-2019
1929	Peter Farb	1959		1980		American author, anthropologist, linguist, ecologist, biologist, and spokesman for conservation 1929-1980
1929	Nigel Glendinning	1959		1991		British scholar and authority on Goya and 18th Century Spanish literature 1929-2013

1929	Tamaz V. Gamkrelidze	1960	1963	2005	Georgian distinguished linguist, orientalist public benefactor and Hittitologist, Academic (since 1974) and President (2005–2013) of the Georgian Academy of Sciences (GAS)	
1929	Lila Gleitman	1960	1967	2000	w	American professor emerita of psychology and linguistics
1929	Richard Mitchell	1960		1991		American professor, first of English and later of classics
1929	Birutė Ciplijauskaitė	1960	1960	2000	w	Lithuanian literary scholar and translator
1929	Peter John Branscombe	1960	1976	2001		British English academic in German studies, a musicologist, and a writer on Austrian cultural history
1929	Charles J. Fillmore	1961	1961	1994		American Professor of Linguistics
1929	José Manuel Briceño Guerrero	1961	1961	2014		Venezuelan writer, philologist and philosopher
1929	Yurij Yakovlevitch Glazov	1961	1962	1990		Russian Indologist known for his studies in Tamil and Malayalam languages and classical literature
1929	Karl V. Teeter	1962	1962	1989		American linguist
1929	Amsalu Aklilu	1962	1962	2002		Ethiopian distinguished lexicographer of Amharic and a language professor
1929	Jehan Desanges	1962		2001		French historian, philologist and epigrapher, a specialist of North Africa during Antiquity
1929	A. K. Ramanujan	1962	1962	1993		Indian poet and scholar[3] of Indian literature who wrote in both English and Kannada
1929	Heinrich Beck	1962	1962	1994		German philologist who specialized in Germanic studies
1929	Jean Briggs	1963	1967	1999	w	American anthropologist, ethnographer, linguist
1929	Byron W. Bender	1963	1963	1995		American professor of linguistics
1929	Michael Harner	1963	1963	1987		American anthropologist, educator and author
1929	Edith Balas	1964	1973	1998	w	Romanian-American Professor of Art History
1929	Eduard Hercigonja	1965	1970			Croatian philologist, Croatist and literary historian
1929	El-Said Badawi	1965	1965	2004		Egyptian scholar and linguist
1929	Howard Clarke	1966		1991		American Professor Emeritus of Classics and Comparative Literature
1929	Якимова Людмила Павловна	1967			w	Russia literary critic (литературоведение поэтика мотив сюжет жанр)

1929	Nicholas Nagy-Talavera	1967	1967	1991	Hungarian-American dissident, historian, writer and professor	1929-2000
1929	Gisela Bleibtreu-Ehrenberg	1969	1970	1991 w	German sociologist, ethnologist, sexologist, and writer further specializing into the fields of psychology, Indo-European studies, religious studies, and philosophy, since 1980 also increasingly anthropology	
1929	H. Arnold Barton	1974		1996	American historian and a national authority on Scandinavian history, especially the history of Sweden, and of Swedes and other Scandinavians in North America	